

THE IMPORTANCE OF MELONS IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY AND PROSPECTS FOR DEVELOPMENT

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The area under crops in the Syrdarya region is 227,816 hectares, including 80,557 hectares of technical crops, 92,900 hectares of grain crops, 520 hectares of legumes, 2,200 hectares of oilseeds, 8,720 hectares of vegetables, 300 hectares of potatoes, 16,380 hectares of melons, 1,761 hectares of orchards, 350 hectares of mulberry silkworms, 72 hectares of vineyards, 20,382 hectares of food crops, 3,674 hectares of other crops. Melons are one of these crops. Farmers of Syrdarya region, as well as other regions of the country, have extensive experience in growing melons. On August 22, 2019, more than 40 varieties of melons were presented at the "Melon Festival".

Melon cultivation has been practiced in Central Asia for centuries, and melons are loved and appreciated by people in the region as one of their most valuable food sources.

According to N.I. Vavilov (1926), Central Asia is a major centre of origin of cultivated plants and a secondary centre for melons, where its diversity is concentrated. Many melon varieties adapted to grow in different soil and climatic conditions of the region have been developed by local breeders. Varieties exist that are adapted to a specific region or even to a specific settlement. Using the genetic diversity of local varieties, new commercial varieties suitable to grow over a wide area have been successfully developed.

Today in Uzbekistan, more than 160 melon varieties—differing in their maturity period, productivity, taste, and fruit shelf life—can be found, and many of them have gained worldwide popularity.

In recent years, 36 melon varieties have been released in Uzbekistan. Among these varieties, some are early ripening (9), midseason ripening (15), and late ripening (12). Eight released varieties are local types. Many varieties now listed in the State Register have been released during the last several decades.

Uzbekistan is the largest zone of melon cultivation in Central Asia. Annually, more than 35 000-40 000 ha of land are devoted to melon cultivation here and the total yield is more than 450 000–500 000 t.

Melons from Central Asia have a great reputation for their unique flavour and sweetness. They have several useful properties. They contain 85–92% water, 8–15% dry matter, 0.8% protein, 1.8% cellulose and 6.2% other carbohydrates, 0.9% fat, 0.6% ash, 20–30 mg% vitamin C, 0.03–0.07 mg% of other vitamins and microelements, such as Zn, Fe, Ca, Mg, K, and P. Sugar content in Central Asian melons can reach up to 14–16%. Sugar can be represented by glucose and/or fructose. This fact adds to relevance to the use of melons as a health food and as medicinal plants. When fructose is prevalent melon pulp is very sweet, and when glucose is prevalent it is somewhat sweet. All these factors define the dietary value of melons, their medicinal properties, and use in human medicine. As a matter of fact, historically famous doctors, such as Iskari Alima (4th century BC), Abu Ali Ibn Sino (a.k.a. Avicenna, 10th century AD) recommended melons for the treatment of many illnesses. Medicinal properties of melons have been confirmed by modern medical science. Melons promote the regulation of many physiological processes. They are used to treat illnesses of the kidneys, stomach, and liver, as well as arteriosclerosis, bronchitis, tuberculosis, rheumatism, and anaemia. An infusion from melon seeds is useful for cough, skin, and gallstone illnesses.

Melons traditionally decorate tables during weddings and other important celebrations. With the same pleasure, fresh melons are eaten by families as part of every day life.

Among many diverse recipes, melon pulp is used in canning and confectionery for the preparation of jam 'shinni', candies, mousse, pies, gingerbread, and cookies.

A special red-brownish honey prepared from cooked melon 'bekmes' is also notable. It contains more than 60% sugar and has an excellent taste. The famous sweet 'halva' can be also prepared with flour. Over-ripe melon fruits with the added bread flour, 'kaunkurt', are another specialty. These are dried in the sun and can be stored in a dry cool place for several months.

Dried in the sun, the sugar content of melons is concentrated (>50%). These slices are used by local populations or exported to other countries.

Melon's skin and unripe fruits are a source of forage for animals. Melon seeds contain up to 35% oil and are used for the preparation of truly high-quality oil.

Changes in modern societies and new trends in agricultural production are influencing the cultivation and spreading of melon varieties. Over the last decade, the local diversity of melon varieties sown by amateurs has fallen, and there is a threat of losing some valuable old varieties that have been selected and maintained by generations of farmers. At the same time, however, the process of improvement of existing local varieties has continued, and new interesting, promising, and stable melon forms and varieties are being produced.

The germplasm of local Central Asian melon varieties is of great value for breeding, and conservation of the melon gene pool is a National interest. For this reason, scientists in Uzbekistan carry out the important work of carefully conserving existing and disappearing local varieties for future generations. This task is carried out through collecting expeditions, conservation in research institutes, and extensive research investigations.

Scientists deploy their efforts on improvement of local varieties for resistance to powdery mildew and Fusarium wilt, and also for the development of new varieties and hybrids. Great attention is paid in the country towards non-polluting melon cultivation, greater use of melon diversity and increased seed production, cultivation of early ripening varieties and hybrids in protected areas, development of rain-fed melon growing processes, and increasing the export of fresh and dried melon products.

REFERENCES:

1.R.Mavlyanova, A.Rustamov, R.Khakimov, A.Khakimov, M.Turdieva and s. Padulosi - Melons of Uzbekistan, 2005

2.Zuev Vladimir Ilich, Qodirxo'jaev Orif, Adilov Maxsud Mirvasitovich, Akramov Umidilla Ikramdjanovich - Vegetable and melon growing.